

4 Training Workshops on GDT

Deliverable N. 1.4

18 July 2024

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Author(s)	Konstantinos Boletsis, Céline Crévisier, Jan Skjetne, Karoline Strand, Ophelia Prillard, Jiaxin Li, Scott Young
Contact	Jan.H.Skjetne@sintef.no
Reviewer	Scott Young (Augment City), Vilija Balionyte-Merle (SINTEF), Catarina Azevedo (INOVA)
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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To foster innovation and co-creation in developing Graphical Digital Twins (GDTs), four introductory workshops were organized for leading and twinning regions within the RESIST project. These workshops aimed to unlock the full potential of GDTs by providing participants with hands-on experience and insights into how GDTs could be tailored and leveraged to address specific regional challenges and drive positive transformations. The workshops additionally facilitated two-way communication, allowing organizers to gather input and feedback for workshop customization and GDT development.

The concept of GDTs was introduced during the World Cafés at the consortium meetings in Coimbra (January 2023) and Turku (June 2023), offering additional opportunities for knowledge exchange and input gathering to ensure the workshops' effectiveness and customization. The first World Café in Coimbra aimed to introduce partners to GDTs. The second, in Turku, focused on using and working with data sources in GDTs.

To summarize the process, four workshops (WS 1, WS 2, WS 3, and WS 4) were conducted:

- **WS 1 (March 31, 2023):** Focused on developing an understanding of GDTs and their application in climate resilience planning. This online session included presentations, used case examples, and breakout discussions to gather insights on the value of using GDTs for the LSDs.
- **WS 2 (June 23, 2023):** Trained super users and data scientists on the tool's capabilities and explored its application in workflows through GDT training and use case examples.
- **WS 3 (November - December 2023):** Defined realistic scenarios to visualize and interact within the GDT, held as a series of four smaller workshops for each LSD and corresponding LSDTs.
- **WS 4 (December 5, 2023):** Demonstrated multiple GDT solutions to showcase possible ways of leveraging GDTs for citizen engagement.

WS 3 and WS 4 leveraged the Needs Assessment (D1.1 and D1.10) of the LSDs, and the use of different visualization tools. Exploring GDTs through this structured approach involving the four key workshops yielded significant benefits:

- **Understanding GDTs (WS 1):** Enabled organizations to harness their advantages effectively.
- **Comprehending data workflows (WS 2):** Established seamless integration and data management processes.
- **Identifying visualization scenarios (WS 3):** Provided valuable insights for process optimization and outcome prediction.
- **Leveraging technologies (WS 4):** Enhanced the attractiveness and engagement of GDT adoption.

Despite some initial challenges in GDT adoption, the workshops tailored to the specific needs of the LSDs, facilitated a co-creation process and guided the development of GDTs. This collaborative

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approach paved the way for successful deployment of demonstrators in multiple regions, contributing to impactful transformations.

Table 1 Overview of World Cafés and Workshops in 2023

	Date	Place	Goal
World Café 1	18 th January , 2023	Coimbra, Portugal	To start the process for all the regions to learn what a GDT was and to start the discussion how this could be used in each region.
World Café 2	29 th June, 2023	Turku, Finland	To leave the participants with a deeper understanding and inspiration of how a GDT could be used to tackle climate resilience planning in their regions.
WS1	31 st of March, 2023	Online	To gain understanding of what a GDT was and how it could be used in climate resilience planning.
WS2	23 rd June, 2023	Online	To train super-users and data scientist in the capabilities of the tool and gain insight into how to apply the tool in a workflow.
WS3	Nov.-Dec., 2023	Online and physical in Ålesund, Norway	To discuss scenarios that LSDs and LSDTs would like to work with, using the GDT. To initiate discussions between LSDs and LSDTs for finding common denominators in their potential scenarios based on their need-assessment documentation.
WS4	5 th Dec., 2023	Ålesund, Norway	To leverage the GDT for stakeholder engagement by providing demonstrations from similar tools and technologies by partners.

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2 INTRODUCTION

To foster innovation, collaboration, and co-creation in developing Graphical Digital Twins (GDTs), WP1 partners (SINTEF and AugmentCity) organized two World Cafés and four introductory workshops for leading and twinning regions. The primary objective was to unlock the full potential of GDTs and to tailor them for the regions within the RESIST project.

The World Cafés initiated discussions among partners, followed by workshops that allowed participants to explore the concepts and opportunities associated with using GDTs in-depth. These workshops facilitated two-way communication and are instrumental in creating GDTs. Participants gained valuable experience in utilizing the tool and understanding the requirements to develop and customize a GDT for their regions.

Engaging in hands-on activities and data visualization with the GDT helped participants develop a deeper understanding of the technology's potential benefits and applications. This knowledge empowered them to identify how GDTs can address their challenges, to make informed decisions, and to drive positive transformations within their regional communities.

A significant outcome of the workshops was the opportunity to introduce early requests for new functionalities. By actively involving participants in the co-creation process, the workshops fostered a collaborative environment where innovative ideas and specific requirements could be shared. This ensures that GDT development aligns closely with the needs and aspirations of the participating regions.

Given the limited number of workshops, planning flexibility was essential. This flexibility allowed adjustments based on the type of information needed for development or the knowledge to be communicated to participants. Additional opportunities, such as consortium meetings, were utilized to gain more insights and make the workshops as effective as possible. Therefore, World Cafés were conducted during consortium meetings in January and June, described in the following part in this report, along with the plan of the four workshops.

To benefit from the Needs Assessment (D1.1 and D1.10) and ensure that different regions were mature enough to discuss potential GDT solutions, the workshops were conducted throughout 2023.

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3 WORLD CAFÉ

A “World Café” is designed to facilitate meaningful and inclusive discussions among a larger group of people. It is a method for hosting discussions on topics of mutual interest and collective exploration. The approach aims to tap into the collective wisdom and knowledge of the participants. The process involves creating a café-like setting where participants gather in smaller groups in separate rooms or tables. It consists of a series of rounds of sessions, lasting around 30 minutes each. At the end of a session the group moves to another table or room for their next session.

The benefit of the World Café approach is that it fosters collaboration and co-creation, by bringing individuals together to share their thoughts and collectively generate new insights. It also benefits from the collective knowledge in a group which allows participants to build upon and refine each other’s ideas.

The World Café processes we conducted were used as a start for the rest of the project consortium to understand the various opportunities, questions and risks surrounding GDT. Understanding participants knowledge base and their experience with GDT helped tailor the workshops further, whilst the open discussions generated ideas and valuable input that could be used in their GDT.

3.1 January 2023

Goal: The goal of the World Café was to start the learning process for all the regions on what a GDT was and to begin the discussion how this could be used in each region.

Description: The World Café last 2 hours. Each of the 4 groups had 30 minutes on the GDT. Each session started with a 10-minute introduction of GDT and a 20-minute discussion among the participants.

Audience: All the participants in the kick-off participated in the World Café but in four different groups which rotated between the stations.

Date & duration: The first World Café was run during the kick-off in Coimbra, Portugal on January 18th in 2023.

Outcome: The discussion on all groups was around two main questions:

- How do you see the GDT working with the pilot?
- How do you envision using the GDT in your region?

Since the concept of GDT was new to most of the participants. The discussion was on a general level and for them to understand the concept. The concrete outcome was the following:

- Virtual exhibition of future impact and solutions
- Transportation – north and south Portugal
- How could they change the model?
- There is a need to have a What-If model
- Visualization of the forest and how to best manage it
- Involve the public
- Used in Rural areas

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- What can WE do to handle climate change?
- Simulation of public services – live and short term

Leveraging: The World Café was an effective tool for initiating discussions about the Graphical Digital Twin (GDT) and starting the process for each region to propose how they might use it. Initially, it was challenging for these groups to provide concrete suggestions. However, the World Café enabled the regions to be more specific, allowing for detailed discussions within the project's scope.

Challenge: The transition from general to concrete solutions and the relation between their own solution and the GDT.

Figure 1 World Café in Coimbra

3.2 June 2023

Goal: The overall goal of this World Café was to leave the participants with a deeper understanding and inspiration of how a GDT can be used to tackle climate resilience planning in their regions. Subsidiary goals focused on how to use the data, the workflow and for the participants to be exposed to some visualization possibilities with the GDT. Within the understanding the use of data goal, the aim was for the participants to discover other data sources, or the combination of various data sources, that could be useful in their GDT. When describing workflows, the goal was for participants to start understanding how to work with data and visualization in a GDT. Showing the participants different visualization possibilities could make increase participants awareness of what visualization was found to be useful and engaging, and perhaps sparked other visualization or interaction ideas through the group discussions.

Description: Each session with the different LSDs followed the same structure, guided by a consistent PowerPoint presentation. The presentation began by emphasizing that the participants were in the "driver's seat," responsible for protecting an area prone to forest fires. Participants were then tasked with discussing and answering questions about the data needed in the GDT to better protect their area from forest fires, identifying the target audience for this information, and considering how it could be visualized effectively.

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Audience: Partners in the project who participated at the Turku consortium meeting (28.-30. June). Approximately 80 participants were grouped into four LSDs, and horizontal partners dispersed across the groups.

Date & duration: 30 min physical meeting per LSD, i.e., 2-hours in total on 29. June in 2023.

Leveraging: The World Café 2 was designed to refine the insights from the World Café 1, based on the findings that indicated participants would benefit from more specific types of GDT knowledge. This session was also developed using the overall insights gained from Workshop 1 and World Café 1.

Outcome: The most important outcome was that participants gained more knowledge. Other outcomes were ideas for data sources, insight into what was important for the participants to protect in their area, and input to the GDT visualization.

Documentation: The World Café used Mentimeter, which was an interactive software platform and could be used to collect information from participants.

Challenges: The World Café moderators were unsure of facilities or equipment would be available for the session. To mitigate this challenge, the moderators brought their own projectors and a screen. Another potential challenge was participants' diverse digital literacy regarding the use of Mentimeter and QR-codes. To negate this challenge the moderators brought Post-it notes and had a plan on using them to replace Mentimeter if needed.

Figure 2 Question from Powerpoint slide

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4 DESCRIPTION OF WORKSHOP PLAN

Description of the task according to the ‘Description of the action (DoA) part A’

“Subtask T1.2.1 Introduction to GDT [M3-M6: Four introductory workshops will be organized for the leading and following regions in the UN Future Lab in Norway to demonstrate the methodologies and tools enabling quintuple helix co-creation approach combined with a site visit and hand-on training on the concepts to be used in RESIST in order to unleash the full potential of the GDT. For this purpose, participants will be able to add and visualize available data from various open data sets (e.g. Copernicus data, national statistics, local and regional municipalities data, and national environmental agencies data) and get insights on how the regional communities may benefit from the GDT. This will help to identify required data sources and formats, expose potential gaps in services/simulations and introduce early requests for new functionalities. ”

This section outlines the development plan for the four workshops, illustrating the timeline, explaining the need for timeline adjustments, and detailing the overall ambitions for the workshops.

4.1 Timeline

The timeline in Figure 3 shows when the workshops and the World Cafés were conducted. The World Cafés are illustrated in orange on the timeline, while the workshops are described in green and blue. The diamond illustrates a specific day, while the rectangle, as for the Workshop 3, means it was carried out over a period of time.

Figure 3 Timeline

4.2 Timeline Adjustment

As described in the DoA, the initial timeline required the 4 workshops to be delivered by end of June 2023. However, following the first consortium meeting and discussion within WP1, risks and opportunities emerged as explained below, and the WP1 partners needed to address these risks and opportunities before the WS3 and WS4 could commence.

Risk and opportunities:

- The work done by the partners in the WP1, especially Adelphi, in the Needs Assessment (D1.1, D1.10) helped create a better and deeper understanding of the regions needs and

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potential use cases for the GDT. That was useful in the WS3 and WS4 discussions for going into specifics about related scenarios and cases that the GDT could be applied for.

- The consortium is very large, 57 partners distributed across Europe with high interest to join the 4 workshops to increase their competence around this cornerstone tool for the RESIST project. Finding common available timeslots for LSDs and their LSDTs was a challenging task that had been originally underestimated.
- The content that provided in the workshops addressed the needs of various audiences and was divided into conceptual/theoretical knowledge on GDTs in general, ideation on the design/development/application of the RESIST GDT, and hands-on demonstrations of already existing GDTs in the consortium, for inspiration purposes. Further theoretical knowledge assimilation and GDT ideation were expected to be triggered and stimulated by the workshops, motivating regions to further research their GDT knowledge and needs.
- Individuals had very different level of understanding of GDT and its benefits, combined with very different levels of digital expertise.

Mitigation actions:

The priority in updating the workshop planning was first and foremost to support the regions so they could leverage the GDT for their projects, which meant increased competences across the consortium on GDT, but also, prepare for GDT to support the regions specific work through tailored use case and finding the right approach for stakeholders' engagement.

- Leveraged the World Café in June to obtain additional inputs on the regional needs.
- Enabled the content-based evolvement of the workshops with WS3 and WS4 to be scheduled after June 2023 to benefit from the findings in the 2 Needs Assessment deliverables (D1.1 and D1.10) and added that knowledge as a starting point for WS3.
- Implemented a hybrid workshop organization, with 3 workshops being held online, in order to 1) offer opportunities for a wider participation across the consortium, while targeting audiences with different technical backgrounds, and 2) provide time to all partners for researching and assimilating the theoretical GDT knowledge, as well as to form tailored ideas and opinions on the RESIST GDT in a high-quality way, without stress and time constraints.
- The last workshop was combined with the consortium visit in Ålesund in December 2023, this gave participants the opportunity to experience several XR-based GDT solutions, including AC's 360 GDT dome facility.

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4.3 Overall Workshops Plan

Table 2 Workshop Overview in 2023

	Format	Targeted audience	Date	Deliverable
WS1: General presentation of what, how and why of GDT	Online presentation	Horizontal partners, LSD1-4 (including their LSDTs): admin personnel, researchers/academia	31 st of March , 2023	Video recording of the workshop – shared on RESIST website
WS2: AC product presentation and workflow workshop	Online presentation 1h including 15min Q&A	Horizontal partners, LSD1-4 (including their LSDTs): admin personnel, researchers/academia	23 rd June, 2023	Video recording – only available for the partners
WS3: Discuss scenarios that LSD would like to work with	The WS was arranged as a series of 4 smaller workshops, 2 were held online, 1 physical in Ålesund and 1 through email	Horizontal partners, LSD1-4 (including their LSDTs): admin personnel, researchers/academia, data specialists	Nov.-Dec., 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report with recommendation of work that can be done in GDT - Inputs for subtask T1.2.3 + T1.2.4
WS4: Leverage the GDT for stakeholder engagement	Physical workshop in Ålesund	Horizontal partners, LSD1-4 (including their LSDTs): admin personnel, researchers/academia, data specialists	5 th Dec., 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report with recommendation for stakeholder engagement through GDT - Inputs for subtask T1.2.3 + T1.2.4

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5 WORKSHOP 1

Goal: To gain understanding of what a GDT was and how it could be used in climate resilience planning.

Targeted audience and participants' list: See Section 4.3 and Appendix 10.1.

Date & duration: The workshop took place on the 31st of March in 2023 and lasted for 2 hours. It was conducted online using the Teams platform, incorporating breakout sessions and a Miro board for collaborative brainstorming.

Leveraging: As an early-stage workshop, there were limited existing resources to leverage. The main objective was to build a foundational understanding of GDT for climate resilience planning.

Details: The workshop was led by CEO Joel Mills, who presented and explained the concept of GDT and why this tool could bring value to climate resilience planning. The session included showcasing use case examples to inspire the audience to think innovatively about new ways of incorporating GDT into their projects, with a breakout session in the latter part of the workshop. Participants were provided access to a Miro board and were given instructions to discuss two key questions:

- "What type of findings would you like to have through the GDT?"
- "What value can you derive from the GDT in the context of your region's climate adaptation project?"

Outcome: The input collected from the breakout session and Miro board served as valuable insights for the project group to plan subsequent workshops and to further refine the project's direction.

Documentation: The workshop was recorded and made available to project partners. Miro boards was created with input from all LSD's and transversal partners.

Challenges: As GDT was likely a new technology and a relatively new concept for many participants, it posed a challenge in making the content easily comprehensible for everyone. The workshop format also faced technical challenges such as connectivity issues, video disruptions, and difficulties accessing the Miro board, which could affect participants' experience and engagement.

Figure 4 Questions

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What is the value you can get from the GDT in the context of your regional climate adaptation project?

Figure 5 Values from GDT

What type of findings would you like to have through the GDT?

Figure 6 Findings through GDT

6 WORKSHOP 2

Goal: To train super-users and data scientist in the capabilities of the tool and gain insight into how to apply the tool in a workflow.

Targeted audience and participants' list: See Section 4.3 and Appendix 10.1.

Date & duration: 10:30-12:00 (1.5h) 23.06.2023

Leveraging: The insights into different region's organization and challenges from the Needs Assessment reports (D1.1 and D1.10) guided the selection of examples of data visualizations and workflows showcased.

Details: The workshop was planned as a 1.5 hour long online session with Teams. Two people from Augment City delivered a PowerPoint presentation and a live demo explaining how certain features work and how the tool could be used. The session was divided in four blocks:

- 1) General training
- 2) Use case examples
- 3) Discussion in breakout sessions
- 4) Wrap up and fill out survey

The general training provided insights into

- What a GDT is
- How to navigate in the GDT
- How to work with a GDT – Scenario management
- Using 3D models, importing data and different data visualizations

The live demo showcased the different features and a project use case example of planning and land management in a rural area.

The session closed with all participants filling out a survey. The survey collection tool used was Typeform. There were five themes for the survey questionnaire:

1. Training Experience: Assess the participants' overall experience and satisfaction with the training session.
2. Understanding of Software and Features: Evaluate the participants' comprehension of the software's basic understanding and key features.
3. Perceived Value and Impact: Measure the participants' perception of the potential value and positive impact the software can have on their daily tasks.
4. Attitude towards Change: Determine if the training session positively affects participants' attitudes towards the new way of working and answers doubts about using new technology.
5. Readiness to Move Forward: Gather insights on participants' preparedness to start using the software and their clarity on the appropriate user roles.

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The survey comprised a mix of yes/no, scaling, and open-ended questions to gather both quantitative and qualitative feedback. Participants were expected to complete it during the session to prevent it from delay responses or becoming an extra task that might be forgotten.

Outcome: A better comprehension of the tool’s abilities amongst the participating regions. Appointment of super users or personnel that likely would use the software.

Documentation: Recording and materials were shared with all participants through e-mail and on SharePoint for other project partners. The survey was reviewed and used to plan the coming workshop and potential other follow-up actions aimed at supporting participants on their GDT journey. Feedback was shared in WP1 meetings.

Challenges: Finding the right attendees in the regions was challenging as this was a new way of working. The session however pushed forward a first selection of appointed potential super users. Having the recording available would help with onboarding potential super users who missed the session.

Figure 7 Workshop setup

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7 WORKSHOP 3

Goal: To discuss scenarios that LSDs and LSDTs would like to work with, using the GDT. To initiate discussions between LSDs and LSDTs for finding common denominators in their potential scenarios based on their need-assessment documentation.

Targeted audience and participants' list: See Section 4.3 and Appendix 10.1.

Date & duration: One 1-hour meeting per LSD/LSDT, i.e., four 1-hour meetings totally, took place between November-December 2023. Doodle invitations per LSD/LSDT were sent out in August. Two LSD/LSDT workshops were held online, one workshop was held physically in Ålesund and one was held in an asynchronous way (due to difficulties in finding available timeslot in November-December) through sending out the workshop content (see Details below) and its description by email.

Leveraging: The Needs Assessment reports (D1.1 and D1.10) have been used as input for suggesting and developing potential LSDs/LSDTs' scenarios to trigger the discussion about the goal, the content, the target group and the application timing of these scenarios during the workshop.

Details: SINTEF Digital utilised the Needs Assessment documents of D1.1 and D1.10 to create a summarized matrix with common attributes that were identified across the needs of all LSDs/LSDTs (Figure 8). Then, two potential scenarios per LSD were formulated to act as examples and triggering factors for the workshop's discussions. AC initiated the workshop with revisiting the basic definition of the GDT and demonstrating a use scenario from AC's portfolio. Then, the summarized need-assessment matrix was presented. Followingly, the two potential scenarios that were formulated and tailored for each LSD, were presented. Then, participants were split in 2 or 3 groups (going in online rooms), where they were asked to work in briefly creating a potential scenario like the two aforementioned examples, by addressing the following questions:

- What do you want to achieve?
- How to use the GDT to achieve the goal?
- Who is the main target groups?
- When or how often will they (i.e., the main target group) would use the tool?

Then, participants returned to the main workshop room and discussed their replies to these questions and their concerns. Naturally, the goal of this exercise was not to come up with finalized scenarios, but to define a structure for scenario development and initialize an ideation and collaborative process regarding scenario development. Finally, a "homework" was given by AC to the participants with two straight-forward questions through a Typeform survey. One was to rate the importance of several GDT use goals (e.g., citizen communication and education, group discussion and decision making, real-time information/warnings, emergency planning, et al.) and then to confirm the problematic theme in their areas (e.g., floods, droughts, coastal erosion, wild fires, heatwaves, et al.). These questions allowed us to clearly evaluate how much the LSDs and LSDTs needs aligned in topics that would define the potential scenarios significantly.

Outcome: A mapping of the basic structure of a scenario and an introduction to the process that could lead to its formulation. Identification of the importance of several GDT use goals and the problematic theme in the LSDs/LSDTs' areas.

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Documentation: The workshop was recorded upon participants' acceptance for internal-to-the-project purposes and uses. The summarized need-assessment matrix and the poll results were made available to the consortium.

Challenges: Finding the most suitable timeslot for each LSD was a challenge that we have mitigated by sending out Doodle invitations before September. Still, almost all workshops had to be rescheduled due to the limited availability of the LSDs/LSDTs at the time. One workshop session (out of four) had to be done asynchronously, through sending out the workshop material by email, due to many difficulties in finding a common timeslot in November and December.

1	LSD	LSDT	Problem addressed	Affected groups by the problem	Current technologies/frameworks/etc.	Future/needed technology	Current data type(s)	Our comments
2	Southwest Finland		Nature-based solutions in water management for urban and rural areas (Incl. stormwater management)	Farmers (crop cultivation, livestock), Forest owners, Agricultural production and forestry sector, Biodiversity, Urban population, citizens, Municipalities, Tourism	visualisation on how sea level rise will impact their coastal line (SWIM 5 SWA)	?	Geospatial	-
3		Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	Flooding of rivers	Farmers, Citizens, Regional authority, Municipalities	ArcGIS/QGIS, modeling software, AI/ML/DL	AI/ML in automatic data analysis	Geospatial	-
4		Normandy	Flooding, marine submersion, erosion, retreat of the coastline	Citizens, Regional authority, ?	Modeling software	?	Geospatial	-
5		Central Denmark	water-related risks such as sea level rise, saltwater intrusion, and interaction between shallow groundwater and rising sea levels.	environmentally harmful companies, cultural heritage sites, citizens, cultural sector, industry and service sector	IoT technology for logging groundwater levels.	explore different construction techniques; machine learning (ML) to track shallow groundwater logging; Test site for "BEST Adapt" tool; XR for education purpose and a warning system app developed through ML and IoT data	Geospatial, statistical data, modeling data?	hydrographic network; meteorological information; statistical data: population data (numbers, distribution);
6		Blekinge	Floods (long term) and Drought (short term). Also Heatwaves.	Private homeowners (sea level rise), farming (flooding, drought), agroforestry (drought), industry (coast, and waters, drought, heatwaves), municipalities, public transport.	Modeling software?	visualize future sea level rising impact related to cultural heritage; visualisation on how sea level rise will impact their coastal line;	Geospatial	
7		Zemgale	flood, extreme weather events like heatwaves, heavy precipitation (in both urban areas and rural sites) and hailstorms and its damages on roofs, solar panels and agricultural land	farming, citizen		Groundwater level monitoring; implement NBS in urban areas		
8		Catalonia	flash floods, wildfires, heat waves, and strong winds.	citizens, farmers, protected natural spaces?	Early Warning Systems (EWS)	improve and extend Early Warning Systems (EWS)	Geospatial, statistical data	geospatial data; water bodies; hydrogeological map; meteorological information; statistical data; population data (numbers, distribution); location of Nature Based Solutions
9		Baiko Alentejo	Excessive precipitation, heat wave, drought, strong wind, frost, particles and dust	citizens, farmers (crop cultivation, livestock), forestry sector, industry, tourism	Different monitoring systems?	Implementation of better tools to assess risks;	Geospatial, statistical data	geospatial data; water courses, hydrographic network, underground water table; statistical data; population data (numbers, distribution); meteorological information; location of Nature Based Solutions
10		Puglia	water management?	?	No available digital tools	?	Geospatial, statistical data	
11		Centro Portugal	Resilience of ecosystems and for goals such as reversing biodiversity loss, ecosystem degradation, and restoration of water cycles, Forest management for rural fire prevention	Diseased, children, elder people, and people in energetic poverty, people living in flood plains, coastlines, or in areas prone to severe storms and other extreme weather events.	ArcGIS, SIG, Decision Support and Emergency Management System	?	Geospatial	
12		Extremadura	Wildfire prevention	Farmers/livestock farmers, forest fire-fighting personnel, Forestry sector, Biodiversity, Rural population, General population	GIS software, Fire modelling software, Advanced statistics software	?	Geospatial	
13		Vesterålen	Not yet clearly defined. Something around Egge-kanten: visualize deep sea and seafloor along with marine biodiversity	local authorities, fishermen, biodiversity, industry, tourism	GIS, projection mapping	?	Geospatial	

Figure 8 The summarized need-assessment matrix for facilitating WS3

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8 WORKSHOP 4

Goal: To leverage the GDT for stakeholder engagement by providing demonstrations from similar tools and technologies by partners. *Subgoals:* Explanation and clarification of the terminology and available GDTs. Hands-on experience with GDTs. Discussions on the use of different GDTs and technologies for various levels of stakeholder engagement.

Targeted audience and participants' list: See Section 4.3 and Appendix 10.1.

Date & duration: Physical workshop in Ålesund, on 5th of December 2023. Full working day (8 hours). All 91 participants tested out the 6 demoed tools and engaged in several discussions (Figure 9 The workshop structure and participants' flow, designed specifically by AC to accommodate all participants experiencing all demos and having meaningful discussions about them. Figure 9).

Leveraging: The horizontal partners' and LSDs' existing GDT tools triggered discussions and ideation on suitable technologies for the GDT that would be further used in T1.2.3 and T1.2.4.

Details: During WS4 in Ålesund, six GDT solutions (Figure 10) were demonstrated to trigger discussion on technical solutions, their benefits/limitations and their performances on citizen and-or stakeholder engagement. AC presented the Smart City 360 Dome and the Captain Deck application, while SINTEF Digital and Museum Nord presented the Gaia Projection Mapping System. VIA University College presented the Danish XR solution, including 360° videos, for visualizing environmental changes. HYDS presented the improvements on the multi-hazard Early Warning System which has been implemented locally in both Terrassa and Blanes (Argos City with the implemented Site-Specific Warnings by UPC) and to Catalonia region (Argos). BTH presented their XR system on visualizing sea level rise. These solutions covered a wide range of GDT-supporting technologies, ranging from desktop applications to Augmented Reality, Projection Mapping, CAVE, and Virtual Reality. As shown in Figure 9, a discussion/feedback sessions were running in parallel with the demo sessions. For the discussion part, notes on Miro board were collected per group or LSD by AC and SINTEF (Figure 11, Figure 12), addressing the following topics:

- Who are the stakeholders we want to reach?
- What type of knowledge do stakeholders currently have and what do they need?
- What kind of decisions do stakeholders take?
- What technology can be used and in which context?
- What are the benefits of certain technologies versus others?
- User Interfaces: how easy / accessible is the technology?
- How can each of the tools be used for these purposes? Positives & negatives.
- What capabilities the tools need to be able to take a decision?

A Typeform questionnaire was also administered with questions regarding the desired GDT user interface, objective, content, visualization, interaction, and navigation, always using the demo applications as starting points and examples.

Outcome: A list of high-level preferences and requirements from LSDs regarding several aspects of the GDT, ranging from target group, use objective, and content to technology, user interface, visualization, and interaction. For instance, based on the Typeform questionnaire, which counted 83 responses, 28% of respondents considered that the desired objective of the GDT should cover both

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alerts and interventions, while 24% leaned solely towards interventions. Also, visualization was desired by the majority to represent data as graphics while navigation should facilitate bird-eye view of areas.

The typeform results also demonstrated that the audience had a good understanding and experience with the different kinds of GDT technologies that have been presented in the consortium meeting. As shown in Figure 13, 70% (77 out of 109) of respondents considered that the GDT was easy to navigate, 83% of respondents considered the interface of GDT easy to understand, and 88% indicated that the scenario visualisation was easy to understand. In general, respondents experienced and evaluated the dimension of “understanding” coming from several experiential elements of the demonstrated GDTs, with the Augmented Reality (VIA), Lower Bridge Dome (AC) and Virtual Reality (BTH) solutions being favoured, while for the other three technologies the respondents’ opinions varied more.

Documentation: The WS4 Miro and Typeform results are available to the consortium. Video recording of the demo sessions and the discussion also took place to be used as promotional material for the project.

Challenges: It was expected that several new suggestions and opinions would appear when discussing technical and technological aspects. To alleviate that, WS4 feedback measures were semi-structured so that discussions always fall under a specific topic.

Figure 9 The workshop structure and participants' flow, designed specifically by AC to accommodate all participants experiencing all demos and having meaningful discussions about them.

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Figure 10 The six demo applications for WS4.

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Figure 11 Overview of the 2 Miro boards that have been used to document the discussion in WS4(Miro board left, Miro board right).

Figure 12 A part of an LSD's Miro board documenting the WS4 discussion.

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Figure 13 Typeform results regarding the audience's understanding of GDT technology.

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9 CONCLUSIONS

Exploring GDTs (Graphical Digital Twins) through a structured approach involving four workshops yielded numerous benefits:

1. **Understanding the Concept (Workshop 1):** Enabled organizations to grasp the potential of GDTs and harness their advantages effectively.
2. **Comprehending the Data Workflow (Workshop 2):** Established seamless integration and data management processes, leading to improved decision-making and operational efficiency.
3. **Identifying Scenarios (Workshop 3):** Helped organizations gain insights, optimize processes, and predict outcomes.
4. **Leveraging Appropriate Technologies (Workshop 4):** Enhanced the attractiveness and engagement of GDTs, enabling organizations to captivate and inform their audience effectively, fostering collaboration and innovation.

This comprehensive approach empowered organizations to maximize the benefits offered by GDTs and to drive impactful transformations in various domains.

During the first World Café, initial challenges were identified related to the willingness to adopt GDTs. Organizations sometimes resisted GDTs due to their own agendas and inherent challenges. Concerns about disrupting established processes, substantial investments, and technical issues such as data integration, interoperability, and cybersecurity also contributed to this resistance. However, experience gained from the workshops has helped increase understanding and decrease resistance.

The workshops initially provided broad, general information about GDTs. To alleviate potential challenges, these gradually focused on the specific needs of LSDs/LSDTs. This approach triggered discussions and a co-creation process, allowing the identification of common elements and attributes for developing the final solution. Leveraging the Needs Assessment (D1.1 and D1.10) results, improved communication with each LSD/LSDT region since June 2023, guiding both back-end (T1.2.2) and front-end (T1.2.3) GDT development and how to verificate/validate solutions which will be developed (T1.2.4). This significantly contributed to reaching M1.2, the development of the first GDT demo tailored to regional needs for fast climate adaptation.

Feedback from WS3 highlighted potential issues with the role of “superusers” as gatekeepers. To address this, the concept of the “digital shepherd” was introduced; an intermediary user-interface built on explainability and user-friendliness to make GDTs accessible to less-technical users. WS4 Typeform survey results provided insights into the understanding and usability of various GDT components, revealing preferred technologies, use types, and potential user-experience challenges.

The co-creation process with LSDs/LSDTs, facilitated by the four workshops, established collaboration in WP3 to guide the deployment of demonstrators in the four LSD regions and eight twinning regions. This collaborative approach ensures that the developed solutions align closely with the needs and aspirations of the participating regions, increasing the likelihood of an effective GDT adoption and impactful transformations.

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10 Appendix

10.1 List of Participants in the 4 Workshops

Table 3 Participants' list in WS1

Approximately 80 people attended WS1, which included horizontal partners and LSD1-4 and their LSDTs: admin personnel, researchers/academia.

Institution	Role
Adelphi	Horizontal Partner
Andfjord Salmon	LSDT4 Twin Vesteralen
Aarhus University	LSDT2 - AU
Augment City	Horizontal Partner
Blanes	LSD 3 - Catalunya
Blekinge	LSDT2 - Blekinge
BTH	LSDT2 - Blekinge
CCDRC	LSD 4 - Centro PT
Central Denmark Region	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
Cerema	LSDT1 - Normandy
CIMBAL/IrRADIARE	LSDT 3 - Baixo Alentejo
CIM-RC	LSD 4 - Centro PT
CIM Médio Tejo	LSD 4 - Centro PT
Danish Coastal Authority	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
DGPF EXTREMADURA	LSD 4 - Centro PT
ERRIN	Horizontal Partner
Forestwise	LSD4 Centro PT
Fundecyt	LSTD4
HYDS	LSD 3 - Catalunya
INOVA+	Horizontal Partner

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INT	LSD3 - Catalunya
IPP	LSD 4 Centro PT
Itecons	LSDT 3 - Baixo Alentejo
KU Leuven	Horizontal Partner
MédioTejo21	LSD 4 Centro PT
Museum Nord v/GaiaVesterålen	LSDT4 Twin Vesteralen
SERN	Horizontal Partner
SINTEF	Horizontal Partner
Southwest Finland	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
Turku AMK	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
Turku	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
UPC	LSD 3 - Catalunya
Vesterålsrådet	LSDT4 - Twin Vesteralen
VIA	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
ZPR	LSDT2 - Zemgale
ZSI	Horizontal Partner

Table 4 Participants' list in WS2

Approximately fifty people from 36 organizations participated in WS2, which included horizontal partners and LSD1-4 and their LSDTs: admin personnel, researchers/academia.

Institution	Role
Adelphi	Horizontal Partner
Andfjord Salmon	LSDT4 Twin Vesteralen
Aarhus University	LSDT2 - AU
Augment City	Horizontal Partner
Blanes	LSD 3 - Catalunya
Blekinge	LSDT2 - Blekinge

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CCDRRC	LSD 4 - Centro PT
Central Denmark Region	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
Cerema	LSDT1 - Normandy
CIMBAL/IrRADIARE	LSDT 3 - Baixo Alentejo
CIM-RC	LSD 4 - Centro PT
CIM Médio Tejo	LSD 4 - Centro PT
Danish Coastal Authority	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
DGPF EXTREMADURA	LSD 4 - Centro PT
ERRIN	Horizontal Partner
Forestwise	LSD4 Centro PT
Fundecyt	LSTD4
HYDS	LSD 3 - Catalunya
INOVA+	Horizontal Partner
INT	LSD3 - Catalunya
IPP	LSD 4 Centro PT
Itecons	LSDT 3 - Baixo Alentejo
KU Leuven	Horizontal Partner
MédioTejo21	LSD 4 Centro PT
Museum Nord v/GaiaVesterålen	LSDT4 Twin Vesterålen
SERN	Horizontal Partner
SINTEF	Horizontal Partner
Southwest Finland	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
Turku AMK	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
Turku	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
UPC	LSD 3 - Catalunya

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Vesterålsrådet	LSDT4 - Twin Vesterålen
VIA	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
ZPR	LSDT2 - Zemgale
ZSI	Horizontal Partner

Table 5 Participants' list in WS3

WS3 was held in a series of 4 workshops, one for each LSD/LSDT. Two workshops were held online, one was held physically in Ålesund, one was held by sending workshop description and materials through email. Approximately 10 people attended each workshop, which included horizontal partners, LSD1-4 and their LSDTs: admin personnel, researchers/academia, data specialists.

Institution	Role
Augment City	Horizontal Partner
RCSF/Valonia	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
Turku	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
RDF EMT	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
NORMANDY REGION	LSDT1- NORMANDY
Cerema	LSDT1 - Normandy
CCDRC	LSD 4 - Centro PT
ERRIN	Horizontal Partner
MédioTejo21	LSD 4 Centro PT
Museum Nord v/GaiaVesterålen	LSDT4 Twin Vesterålen
UEX - EXTREMADURA	LSD 4 Centro PT
SINTEF	Horizontal Partner
Blekinge*	LSDT2 - Blekinge
Aarhus University*	LSDT2 - AU
Central Denmark Region*	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
Danish Coastal Authority*	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
ZPR*	LSDT2 - Zemgale

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CIMBAL**	LSDT 3 - Baixo Alentejo
HYDS**	LSD 3 - Catalunya
Terrassa**	LSD 3 - Catalunya
UPC**	LSD 3 - Catalunya
UOC**	LSD 3 - Catalunya
INT**	LSD 3 - Catalunya
TECNOPOLIS**	LSDT3 - TecnoPolis
BLANES**	LSD 3 - Catalunya
Pulgia**	LSDT 3 - Pulgia

Organization with * indicates that the workshop was conducted physically at the Ålesund Consortium meeting.

Organization with ** indicates that it was conducted through distributing workshop materials through email.

Table 6 Participants' list in WS4

Approximately 70 people attended WS4, which included horizontal partners, LSD1-4 and their LSDTs: admin personnel, researchers/academia, data specialists.

Institution	Role
Adelphi	Horizontal Partner
Andfjord Salmon	LSDT4 Twin Vesteralen
Aarhus University	LSDT2 - AU
Augment City	Horizontal Partner
Blanes	LSD 3 - Catalunya
Blekinge	LSDT2 - Blekinge
BTH	LSDT2 - Blekinge
CCDRC	LSD 4 - Centro PT
Central Denmark Region	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
Cerema	LSDT1 - Normandy
CIMBAL/IrRADIARE	LSDT 3 - Baixo Alentejo

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CIM Médio Tejo	LSD 4 - Centro PT
Danish Coastal Authority	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
DGPF EXTREMADURA	LSD 4 - Centro PT
ERRIN	Horizontal Partner
Forestwise	LSD4 Centro PT
Fundecyt	LSTD4
HYDS	LSD 3 - Catalunya
INOVA+	Horizontal Partner
INT	LSD3 - Catalunya
IPP	LSD 4 Centro PT
Itecons	LSDT 3 - Baixo Alentejo
KU Leuven	Horizontal Partner
MédioTejo21	LSD 4 Centro PT
Museum Nord v/GaiaVesterålen	LSDT4 Twin Vesteralen
SERN	Horizontal Partner
SINTEF	Horizontal Partner
Southwest Finland	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
Turku AMK	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
Turku	LSD 1 Southwest Finland
UPC	LSD 3 - Catalunya
Vesterålsrådet	LSDT4 - Twin Vesteralen
VIA	LSD 2 - Central Denmark Region
ZPR	LSDT2 - Zemgale
ZSI	Horizontal Partner

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